

A study on viscosities of some bivalent transition metal nitrates and magnesium nitrate in aqueous and binary aqueous mixtures of DMF at different temperatures

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Abstract : Viscosities for the solutions of some bivalent transition metal nitrates viz. manganese nitrate, cobalt nitrate, nickel nitrate, copper nitrate and zinc nitrate; and magnesium nitrate, at different concentrations have been determined in aqueous and in binary aqueous mixtures of *N,N*-dimethyl formamide (DMF) at 303.15 K and in aqueous and in 5% (w/w) DMF + water at five different temperatures. The data have been evaluated using the Jones-Dole equation and the obtained parameters have been interpreted in terms of ion-ion and ion-solvent interactions. The activation parameters of viscous flow have been obtained which depicts the mechanism of viscous flow. The transition metal nitrates and magnesium nitrate act as structure breakers in aqueous and in binary aqueous mixtures of DMF.

Keywords : Viscosity, metal nitrates, mixed solvent.

Addition of organic solvent to an aqueous solution of electrolyte brings about a change in ion's solvation and often results in a large change in the reactivity of dissolved electrolyte^{1,2}. The use of amide + water mixtures has attracted much attention in recent years as solvents in the study of physico-chemical properties of electrolytic solutions³⁻⁶. The aim of the present study is to present new informations on the interaction of DMF + water systems from chemical and biology point of view.

Results and discussion

The relative viscosities and densities of the solutions of bivalent transition metal nitrates : manganese nitrate, cobalt nitrate, nickel nitrate, copper nitrate, zinc nitrate and magnesium nitrate in water and in binary aqueous mixtures of DMF (5, 10, 15, 20 and 25% by weight of DMF) were measured at 303.15 K and analysed by the Jones-Dole equation⁷ :

$$\eta_{rel} = \eta/\eta_0 = 1 + Ac^{1/2} + Bc, \quad (1)$$

where η and η_0 are the viscosities of the solution and solvent (water, water + DMF) respectively, and c is the molar concentration, A and B are the constants characteristic of ion-ion and ion-solvent interactions respectively.

The plots of $[\eta_r - 1]/\sqrt{c}$ versus \sqrt{c} for all the nitrates, were found to be linear. The values of A and B

parameters have been calculated using the least squares method by fitting the experimental results in the Jones-Dole equation and these values are given in Table 1.

Table 1 shows that the values of A -coefficients are generally positive but very small in magnitude for an individual electrolyte in water and in the entire composition range of DMF + water at 303.15 K thereby showing the presence of weak ion-ion interactions. It is also clear from Table 1 that the value of A -coefficient continuously decreases with increase of DMF content in water at 303.15 K, for an individual electrolyte, showing that ion-ion interactions are weakened by the addition of DMF to water. These results indicate that the transition metal nitrates and magnesium nitrate mix more ideally with DMF + water as compared to water and there is a perfect solvation of these nitrates in higher compositions of DMF + water mixtures resulting in weak ion-ion interactions.

B -Coefficients are positive for all the nitrates in water and in binary aqueous mixtures of DMF and increase with increase in DMF composition in water suggesting that the ion-solvent interactions are further strengthened with increase of DMF content in water.

The magnitude of B -coefficients, is larger compared to A -coefficients showing that ion-solvent interactions

Table 1. Values of *A* and *B* parameters of Jones-Dole equation for transition metal nitrates and magnesium nitrate in water and DMF + water mixtures at 303.15 K

Standard errors are given in parentheses

DMF + water (% w/w)	<i>A</i> (dm ^{-3/2} mol ^{-1/2})	<i>B</i> (dm ³ mol ⁻¹)
Manganese nitrate		
0 (water)	0.065 (±0.002)	0.216 (±0.001)
5	0.068 (±0.003)	0.375 (±0.001)
10	0.039 (±0.005)	0.431 (±0.001)
15	0.016 (±0.006)	0.479 (±0.001)
20	-0.002 (±0.004)	0.513 (±0.001)
25	-0.016 (±0.008)	0.534 (±0.002)
Cobalt nitrate		
0 (water)	0.035 (±0.004)	0.235 (±0.001)
5	0.039 (±0.002)	0.295 (±0.001)
10	0.028 (±0.004)	0.310 (±0.001)
15	0.017 (±0.003)	0.331 (±0.001)
20	0.006 (±0.004)	0.349 (±0.001)
25	-0.008 (±0.002)	0.377 (±0.001)
Nickel nitrate		
0 (water)	0.091 (±0.005)	0.249 (±0.007)
5	0.031 (±0.002)	0.194 (±0.001)
10	0.020 (±0.004)	0.212 (±0.001)
15	0.008 (±0.002)	0.238 (±0.000)
20	0.000 (±0.003)	0.247 (±0.000)
25	-0.007 (±0.003)	0.262 (±0.000)
Copper nitrate		
0 (water)	0.040 (±0.001)	0.200 (±0.001)
5	0.027 (±0.005)	0.381 (±0.001)
10	0.013 (±0.003)	0.408 (±0.001)
15	0.003 (±0.002)	0.423 (±0.001)
20	-0.006 (±0.001)	0.445 (±0.001)
25	-0.015 (±0.004)	0.466 (±0.001)
Zinc nitrate		
0 (water)	0.036 (±0.001)	0.283 (±0.001)
5	0.059 (±0.001)	0.205 (±0.001)
10	0.041 (±0.005)	0.238 (±0.001)
15	0.024 (±0.002)	0.278 (±0.001)
20	0.010 (±0.006)	0.297 (±0.001)
25	-0.002 (±0.005)	0.319 (±0.001)
Magnesium nitrate		
0 (water)	0.043 (±0.006)	0.194 (±0.004)
5	0.053 (±0.003)	0.374 (±0.002)
10	0.036 (±0.006)	0.402 (±0.001)
15	0.024 (±0.002)	0.414 (±0.001)
20	0.005 (±0.004)	0.441 (±0.001)
25	-0.008 (±0.002)	0.459 (±0.001)

dominate over the ion-ion interactions. Moreover, the value of *B*-coefficient is influenced to a considerable extent on addition of DMF to water showing that the solvation of ions is influenced in aquo-organic medium.

The viscosity data have also been analysed on the basis of transition state treatment of relative viscosity. The *B* parameter in terms of this theory is given by the following relation :

$$B = \frac{\overline{V}_1^0 - \overline{V}_2^0}{1000} + \frac{\overline{V}_1^0}{1000} \left[\frac{\Delta\mu_2^{0*} - \Delta\mu_1^{0*}}{RT} \right] \quad (2)$$

where \overline{V}_1^0 is the mean volume of the solvent and \overline{V}_2^0 the partial molar volume of the electrolyte. The free energy of activation per mole of pure solvent ($\Delta\mu_1^{0*}$), and the free energy of activation per mole of electrolyte ($\Delta\mu_2^{0*}$) were calculated⁸ with the help of relations (3) and (4) respectively :

$$\Delta\mu_1^{0*} = RT \ln (\eta_0 \overline{V}_1^0 / hN) \quad (3)$$

and

$$\Delta\mu_2^{0*} = \Delta\mu_1^{0*} + RT/\overline{V}_1^0 [1000 B - (\overline{V}_1^0 - \overline{V}_2^0)] \quad (4)$$

where *h* is the Planck's constant, *N* the Avogadro number, η_0 the viscosity of solvent, *R* the gas constant and *T* the absolute temperature. The values of $\Delta\mu_1^{0*}$, calculated from relation (3) are given in Table 2.

For mixed solvents, each solvent mixture was treated as pure and the molar volume taken as a mean volume defined as⁹ :

$$\overline{V}_1^0 = [x_1 M_1 + x_2 M_2]/d_1 \quad (5)$$

here $x_1 M_1$ and $x_2 M_2$ are the mole fractions and molecular weights of water and DMF respectively, and d_1 is the density of solvent (DMF + water). The values of \overline{V}_2^0 , the partial molar volume at infinite dilution for transition metal nitrates and magnesium nitrate, determined from density data, are also recorded in Table 2. The values of $\Delta\mu_2^{0*}$ and \overline{V}_1^0 , calculated with the help of relations (4) and (5) respectively, are also recorded in Table 2.

It is evident from Table 2 that $\Delta\mu_1^{0*}$ is practically constant at all solvent compositions implying that $\Delta\mu_2^{0*}$ is dependent mainly on *B*-coefficient and $(\overline{V}_1^0 - \overline{V}_2^0)$ terms. $\Delta\mu_2^{0*}$ are positive and larger than $\Delta\mu_1^{0*}$ suggesting the transition state is less favoured in the presence of nitrates, showing the formation of transition state is accompanied by the breaking and distortion of the intermolecular bonds between DMF and water.

Table 2. Values of \overline{V}_1^0 ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$), \overline{V}_2^0 ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$), $\Delta\mu_1^{0*}$ (kJ mol^{-1}) and $\Delta\mu_2^{0*}$ (kJ mol^{-1}) for transition metal nitrates and magnesium nitrate in different compositions of DMF + water at 303.15 K

Parameter	DMF + water (% w/w)				
	5	10	15	20	25
\overline{V}_1^0	18.79	19.57	20.40	21.31	22.30
$\Delta\mu_1^{0*}$	61.67	62.05	62.37	62.66	62.96
Manganese nitrate					
\overline{V}_2^0	199.18	225.71	234.98	241.61	245.35
$\Delta\mu_2^{0*}$	136.10	144.17	148.11	148.51	149.46
Cobalt nitrate					
\overline{V}_2^0	149.64	150.43	151.83	153.73	154.82
$\Delta\mu_2^{0*}$	118.75	129.45	134.48	137.84	139.07
Nickel nitrate					
\overline{V}_2^0	189.93	199.34	203.87	210.92	219.95
$\Delta\mu_2^{0*}$	110.59	112.60	114.33	114.38	114.87
Copper nitrate					
\overline{V}_2^0	183.97	190.58	204.49	218.57	234.10
$\Delta\mu_2^{0*}$	134.94	136.41	137.41	138.60	139.50
Zinc nitrate					
\overline{V}_2^0	162.29	167.58	176.00	182.02	189.42
$\Delta\mu_2^{0*}$	108.37	111.82	115.92	116.81	117.94
Magnesium nitrate					
\overline{V}_2^0	187.98	215.04	238.38	244.58	257.40
$\Delta\mu_2^{0*}$	134.46	139.01	139.18	141.23	141.44

Effect of temperature :

The effect of temperature has been studied in water and in 5% (w/w) DMF + water. The plots of $[\eta_r - 1]/\sqrt{c}$ versus \sqrt{c} have been found to be linear at all temperatures in accordance with the Jones-Dole equation (1). Values of *A* and *B* parameters have been calculated using the least squares method and are given in Table 3.

The values of *A* are either positive or negative for individual nitrate in water as well as in DMF + water (5% w/w) mixture and decrease with rise in temperature, suggesting ion-ion interactions are weakened with increase in temperature.

The values of *B*-coefficient are positive showing presence of strong ion-solvent interactions. *B*-Coefficient increases with rise in temperature suggesting ion-solvent interactions are strengthened with the rise in temperature for all the nitrates in water and DMF + water.

Table 3. Values of parameters *A* ($\text{dm}^{3/2} \text{mol}^{-1/2}$) and *B* ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$) of Jones-Dole equation for transition metal nitrates and magnesium nitrate in water and in DMF + water (5% w/w) at different temperatures. Error ($\pm 2 \times 10^{-3}$)

Parameter	Temperature (K)				
	298.15	303.15	308.15	313.15	318.15
	Water				
Manganese nitrate					
A	0.082	0.065	0.050	0.038	0.017
B	0.187	0.216	0.236	0.261	0.267
Cobalt nitrate					
A	0.058	0.035	0.017	0.009	-0.003
B	0.168	0.235	0.250	0.272	0.295
Nickel nitrate					
A	0.125	0.091	0.054	0.031	0.002
B	0.025	0.249	0.307	0.363	0.380
Copper nitrate					
A	0.050	0.040	0.021	0.004	-0.004
B	0.173	0.200	0.260	0.310	0.331
Zinc nitrate					
A	0.049	0.036	0.020	0.004	-0.004
B	0.270	0.283	0.318	0.342	0.352
Magnesium nitrate					
A	0.058	0.043	0.002	-0.001	-0.007
B	0.159	0.194	0.246	0.301	0.314
	5% (w/w) DMF + water				
Manganese nitrate					
A	0.90	0.068	0.046	0.020	0.007
B	0.365	0.375	0.384	0.440	0.453
Cobalt nitrate					
A	0.056	0.039	0.022	0.013	-0.001
B	0.283	0.295	0.314	0.342	0.410
Nickel nitrate					
A	0.050	0.031	0.001	-0.006	-0.008
B	0.157	0.194	0.258	0.302	0.324
Copper nitrate					
A	0.049	0.027	0.009	-0.010	-0.012
B	0.324	0.381	0.409	0.429	0.449
Zinc nitrate					
A	0.086	0.059	0.039	0.012	-0.007
B	0.147	0.205	0.238	0.297	0.339
Magnesium nitrate					
A	0.098	0.053	0.098	-0.001	-0.014
B	0.309	0.374	0.422	0.450	0.468

The value of dB/dT is positive for all the transition metal nitrates and magnesium nitrate in water as well as in DMF + water showing that the transition metal ni-

trates and magnesium nitrate act as structure breakers in both the systems.

B-Coefficients at different temperatures have also been analysed by applying the transition state theory. The values of $\Delta\mu_1^{0*}$ and $\Delta\mu_2^{0*}$ have been calculated with the help of relations (3) and (4) respectively, and are recorded in Table 4.

Table 4. Values of V_1^0 ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$), V_2^0 ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$), $\Delta\mu_1^{0*}$ (kJ mol^{-1}) and $\Delta\mu_2^{0*}$ (kJ mol^{-1}) in DMF + water (5% w/w) at different temperatures

Parameter	Temperature (K)				
	298.15	303.15	308.15	313.15	318.15
V_1^0	18.76	18.79	18.82	18.86	18.90
$\Delta\mu_1^{0*}$	61.00	61.67	62.38	63.13	63.93
Manganese nitrate					
V_2^0	192.04	199.18	206.92	212.25	220.51
$\Delta\mu_2^{0*}$	132.06	136.10	140.26	150.59	155.58
Cobalt nitrate					
V_2^0	142.78	149.64	154.52	156.95	160.17
$\Delta\mu_2^{0*}$	115.21	118.75	123.64	129.42	141.06
Nickel nitrate					
V_2^0	175.10	189.93	212.13	217.96	231.65
$\Delta\mu_2^{0*}$	102.36	110.59	123.74	132.37	139.11
Copper nitrate					
V_2^0	171.40	183.97	194.64	204.81	215.37
$\Delta\mu_2^{0*}$	123.99	134.94	141.99	150.72	154.23
Zinc nitrate					
V_2^0	151.53	162.29	188.17	193.38	196.55
$\Delta\mu_2^{0*}$	98.00	108.37	117.83	128.24	136.28
Magnesium nitrate					
V_2^0	183.98	187.98	194.39	197.62	202.18
$\Delta\mu_2^{0*}$	133.60	134.46	143.73	149.98	155.13

According to Feakins model¹⁰, $\Delta\mu_2^{0*}$ increases with temperature for solutes having positive values of dB/dT , which act as structure breakers in water as well as in DMF + water.

The change in activation energy per mole of solute is positive and large for all the nitrates studied in 5% (w/w) DMF + water at different temperatures. The formation of the transition state is less favoured in the presence of nitrates in the entire range of temperature.

The entropy of activation for transition metal nitrates and magnesium nitrate has also been calculated from the relation¹⁰ :

$$d(\Delta\mu_2^{0*})/dT = -\Delta S_2^{0*} \quad (6)$$

The values of ΔS_2^{0*} have been calculated from the slopes of linear plots of $\Delta\mu_2^{0*}$ versus T , by using the least squares method. The values of $T\Delta S_2^{0*}$ at different temperatures and the activation enthalpy (ΔH_2^{0*}) calculated with the help of expression¹⁰ :

$$\Delta H_2^{0*} = \Delta\mu_2^{0*} + T\Delta S_2^{0*} \quad (7)$$

are recorded in Table 5.

Table 5. Entropy, $T\Delta S_2^{0*}$ (KJ mol^{-1}) and enthalpy, ΔH_2^{0*} (kJ mol^{-1}) of activation for viscous flow of transition metal nitrates and magnesium nitrate in DMF + water (5% w/w) at different temperatures

Parameter	Temperature (K)				
	298.15	303.15	308.15	313.15	318.15
Manganese nitrate					
$T\Delta S_2^{0*}$	-366.85	-373.00	-379.15	-385.31	-391.46
ΔH_2^{0*}	-234.79	-236.90	-238.89	-234.72	-235.58
Cobalt nitrate					
$T\Delta S_2^{0*}$	-371.93	-378.16	-384.40	-390.64	-396.87
ΔH_2^{0*}	-256.72	-259.41	-260.76	-261.22	-255.81
Nickel nitrate					
$T\Delta S_2^{0*}$	-568.09	-577.61	-587.14	-596.67	-606.19
ΔH_2^{0*}	-465.73	-467.02	-463.40	-464.30	-467.08
Copper nitrate					
$T\Delta S_2^{0*}$	-454.72	-462.34	-469.97	-477.59	-485.22
ΔH_2^{0*}	-330.73	-327.40	-327.98	-326.87	-330.99
Zinc nitrate					
$T\Delta S_2^{0*}$	-574.85	-584.49	-594.13	-603.77	-613.41
ΔH_2^{0*}	-476.85	-476.12	-476.30	-475.53	-477.13
Magnesium nitrate					
$T\Delta S_2^{0*}$	-468.56	-476.42	-484.28	-492.14	-499.99
ΔH_2^{0*}	-334.96	-341.96	-340.55	-342.16	-344.86

Both enthalpy and entropy of activation are negative for all the transition metal nitrates and magnesium nitrate, in 5% (w/w) DMF + water mixture at different temperatures, which suggest that the transition state is associated with bond breaking and increase in order. Although a detailed mechanism for this cannot be easily advanced, it may be suggested that the slip-plane is in the disordered state.

Experimental

AnalaR quality manganese nitrate [$\text{Mn}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$], cobalt nitrate [$\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$], nickel nitrate [$\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$], copper nitrate [$\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$], zinc nitrate [$\text{Zn}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$] and magnesium nitrate [$\text{Mg}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$] were used. Distilled water (sp. cond.

$\approx 10^{-6} \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) was used for preparing solutions and binary aqueous mixtures of DMF as well as standard liquid.

All the binary aqueous mixtures of DMF as well as the solutions of nitrates were made by weight and molarities, m , were converted into molarities, c using the standard expression¹¹ : $c = 100 \text{ dm} / (1000 + mM_2)$, where d is the solution density and M_2 the molecular weight of an solute.

For density measurements, an apparatus similar to the one reported by Ward and Millero¹² and described elsewhere¹³ was used. The relative viscosities were measured at the desired temperature using Ostwald's suspended level type viscometer, with a flow time 341 s for water at 303.15 K (± 0.01 K). Since all the flow times were greater than 100 s, kinetic energy correction was not necessary. The relative viscosities of the solutions (η_{rel}) were calculated by the usual procedure¹³.

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